

ENVIRONMENTAL INFLUENCE ON CHARACTER EDUCATION AT BALI STATE POLYTECHNIC

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Abstract

This research was conducted to describe whether there is an environmental influence on character education at the Bali State Polytechnic. This research is motivated by efforts to build student character on campus through environmental learning. So far, character education on campus is still hampered by problems with learning methods or models. With this research, it is hoped that there will be new findings regarding the character education learning model, as well as its influence on student character formation. The research method used was a correlational quantitative approach which took place at the Bali State Polytechnic. The instruments used to collect data were questionnaires, observations and interviews. Meanwhile, the informants in this research were lecturers and students at the Bali State Polytechnic. The results of the research show that the implementation of character education at the Bali State Polytechnic can be carried out well, this is measured by learning achievement, student activity, a pleasant learning atmosphere and can build students' independent understanding. Meanwhile, the level of character formed from this learning is: (1) Honesty (2) Discipline (3) Care for the Environment. Where the value of honesty increased by an average of 32%, the value of discipline increased by an average of 40% and environmental care increased by an average of 35%. The results of the t-test on the influence of the environment on character education are $t_{table} = 2.363 > t_{count} = -12.146$, so H_0 or hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that the environment has a very significant influence on character education.

Keywords: Environment, Character Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Humans need the environment to be a place for life to take place and likewise the environment needs humans to preserve the environment (Aziz (2013). Human behavior can influence the environment and the environment can also influence human behavior. (Azhar, & Alfitri. (2015). Environment is to maintain the overall quality of life; to maintain continuing access to natural resources to avoid lasting environmental damage; problem because the environment continues to be used for human prosperity without adhering to the principle of sustainability (Harahap, et al, 2018).

Human behavior towards the environment is usually influenced by the awareness of the importance of the environment for the survival of each individual (Taufiq, 2014). No matter how small the effort in protecting the environment, it is an indispensable first step in creating a healthy and sustainable environment. In exploring, children can use all their senses by touching, tasting, smelling, mixing, comparing what they see (Kustiani, 2015). So, the environment is the most appropriate and very broad means for exploration. Through creative and innovative activities, children will be interested and begin to increase their curiosity. Thus, the environment can provide good encouragement for children's development. "Contextual

plural intelligence" A concept that is open minded towards more creative, active participatory, and meaningful and enjoyable learning needs (Rachmadtullah, 2018).

Character is a characteristic possessed by an object or individual. These characteristics are original and rooted in the personality of the object or individual, and are the "engine" that drives how a person acts, speaks, behaves and responds to things (Kertajaya, 2010). Character education is a way of thinking and behaving that is characteristic of each individual to live and work together, both within the family, community, nation and state (Suyanto, 2009). Meanwhile, the concept of character education proposed by Nuraeni & Labudasari (2021) is a conscious effort to develop good character based on basic policies (hidden virtues) which are objectively beneficial for both individuals and society. Thus, it can be concluded that character education is an effort to foster and develop student character (Subianto, 2013). Character development of the nation's children must be the main concern. One thing that must be considered and developed is behavior to care for the environment. Students must be trained from an early age to be responsive to environmental problems, so that an attitude of ignorance towards the environment does not arise. Children must also be educated to have morals, a responsible attitude and a high sense of concern for their environment. Students are expected to have 18 characters, namely honest, tolerant, religious, hardworking, disciplined, independent, creative, curious, democratic, love the country, sociable, passionate about the nation, likes to read, loves peace, cares socially, cares about the environment, appreciates achievements, and responsibility (Irhamna & Purnama, (2022). According to), the character education learning model is carried out using various models, namely: 1) habituation and example; 2) CTL (Contextual Teaching and Learning); 3) role playing; 4) participative learning (participative instruction). The importance of character education is everything that is inherent in an individual and tends to remain there. Therefore, character education forms an individual's tendency to have good character and be useful to others. Therefore, character education for teenagers is very important (Mulyasa (2016: 165).

However, in fact, children's behavior in this era of globalization is getting worse due to increasingly free and uncontrolled social interactions, the increasing number of criminal acts and crimes committed by elementary school age children, due to the increasing loss of moral norms so that education is needed which can be used as a forum for character building in students. And as a means of formal education that focuses on education (Nugroho, 2020). Based on observations, children who attend conventional schools tend not to be given the opportunity to explore more actively, the activities they do only use objects around them (Rahmawati dan Kurniati, 2010).

That exploring will give children the opportunity to understand and utilize their exploration in the form of; Wider and more real insight into information, fostering children's curiosity about something they already know or have just discovered. Through exploration, you can clarify the concepts and skills you already have, gain a full understanding of human life with various existing situations or conditions. Then, children gain knowledge about how to understand the environment around them and how to use it (Rahmawati & Kurniati, 2010). The open building (without partitions) is also designed so that children are one with nature. Children are educated

not only to study general subjects, but here children are taught how to love nature and care about the environment, taught how to be responsible and have noble morals. Developing his potential to have spiritual strength, self-control, personality and intelligence (Nadiroh & Hasanah, 2018).

2. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is a quantitative correlational approach. That is, researchers use statistical research instruments to test hypotheses. According to Sugiyono (2017:8) Quantitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing hypotheses that have been applied. This research includes questionnaire research because this research aims to determine the influence of the campus environment on the formation of student character. The researcher will give a questionnaire to the sample that has been determined, namely class IVA students, and the questionnaire contains questions that must be answered by the respondent. In this research, researchers conducted research on the influence of the campus environment on the character formation of class IVA students at the Bali State Polytechnic Tourism Department. In this research, there is one independent variable, namely the environment, and a dependent variable, namely character formation (Anggriani et al., 2019).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

3.1 Results of the Research

The formation of student character cannot only be realized in the form of understanding, but also requires aspects of implementation or practice. Choosing an environmental learning model as a new alternative in forming students' character at school is the right choice because it has the advantage, apart from being constructive about their own knowledge, it also involves their experience to practice in a small scope on campus. Student character will be formed if the campus environment implements a good campus culture, because students will of course imitate what an educator does (Nurdin, 2020). Therefore, researchers interviewed lecturer respondents to find out how the campus attempts to shape student character within the Bali State Polytechnic environment. Based on the results of an interview with a lecturer as head of the tourism department, "Character education has been implemented with the term "Green Ethics". The preparations made by the campus are by setting an example of an attitude of "honesty, discipline and concern for the environment", in addition to not using plastic materials in every activity. "Before starting learning, students are asked to pray first, according to their respective beliefs." According to Ismail (2021), instilling character in students is done by giving them positive examples, so that they can become role models for students. In this process, the author first observes the condition of the campus environment, taking into account the physical environment, social environment, academic environment, and learning and teaching processes (PBM):

Table 1: Observations on Student Character Formation

No	Value	Character Aspects observed	Done	
			Yes	No
1	Honest	a). Don't take things that don't belong to you. b). Don't cheat or give answers. c). Don't spread unclear rumors.		
2.	Discipline	a). Lecturers and students arrive before the appointed time. b). Enforcing principles by providing punishment for those who violate and rewards for those who excel. c). Comply with campus rules and regulations.		
3.	Environmental care	a). Throw garbage in its place. b). Using recycled products. c). Know how to care for plants and not damage plants around campus.		

Before character formation was carried out, the researcher conducted a pretest on 30 students with the following results: 1) Honest Character 14 people (47%), with an average score of 7.5, 2) Discipline 10 people (33%) with an average score of 7.1, and 3) Care for the Environment 6 people (20%) with an average score of 6.8.

Figure 1: Character formation diagram

If it is looked at the diagram above, the character of caring for the environment is ranked the lowest, namely 6%, meaning awareness about the environment is still very low. Meanwhile, discipline is in second place, namely 30%, meaning discipline in character formation needs to be improved, and honesty is in first place, namely 43%, meaning honesty needs to be improved, so that it can reach 100%.

3.1.1 Results of the First Meeting

After the formation of student character in the campus environment which was carried out at the first meeting with the final grades as follows: 1) The character of honesty, the number of students who have not developed (MB) is 19 students (53%), while students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and are developing very good (BSB) 11 people (36.37%). 2) Disciplinary character, the number of students who have not yet developed (MB)

is 20 students (67%), while there are 10 students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB). 3) The character of caring for the environment, the number of students who have not yet developed (MB) is 22 students (73%), while the students who develop according to expectations (BSH) and develop very well (BSB) are 8 people. Researchers can conclude that there are still many students who are underdeveloped. As can be seen in the following diagram:

Figure 2: Diagram of Character Formation Achievements

From Figure 2 above, it can be explained that the stages of development of children's character formation at the first learning meeting are: 1) The character of caring for the environment occupies the lowest position that has developed (BB), namely 8 people, 2) The character of discipline occupies the second position that has developed (BB), namely 10 people 3) The character of honesty occupies the first position with a number that has developed, namely 11 people. This can be concluded from the 3 indicators that character development needs to be further improved.

3.1.2 Research Results of the Second Meeting

After the formation of student character in the campus environment which was carried out at the second meeting with the final grades as follows: 1) Honesty character, the number of students who have not developed (SB) is 10 students (33%), while students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and very well developed (BSB) 20 people. 2) Disciplinary character, the number of students who have not developed (BB) is 13 students (43%), while there are 17 students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB). 3) The character of caring for the environment, the number of students who have not yet developed (BB) is 16 people (53%), while the number of students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB) is 14

people. Researchers can conclude that there are still many students who are underdeveloped, so they need to improve as can be seen in the following diagram:

Figure 3: Diagram of Character Formation Achievements

From figure 3 above, it can be explained that the development stage of student character formation increased at the second research meeting compared to the first meeting, namely: 1) Environmentally caring character increased by an average of 20%, 2) Disciplinary character increased by an average of 24% and 3) Honesty character increases by an average of 20%. Meanwhile, students who developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB) from the three variables on average increased by 26.67%, meaning that they need to be improved further.

3.1.3 Research Results of the Third Meeting

The formation of student character in the campus environment was carried out at the third meeting with the final grades as follows: 1) The character of honesty, the number of students who have not developed (BB) is 3 (10%), while students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and have developed very well. good (BSB) 27 people. 2) Disciplinary character, the number of students who have not yet developed (BB) is 4 students (13%), while there are 26 students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB). 3) The character of caring for the environment, the number of students who have not yet developed (BB) is 6 people (20%), while the number of students who have developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB) is 24 people. Researchers can conclude that there are still some students who are not developing enough, so they need to improve as can be seen in the following diagram:

Figure 4: Diagram of Character Formation Achievements

From the picture. 4 above, it can be explained that the development stage of student character formation has increased at the third research meeting, this is proven by: 1) The character of caring for the environment has increased by an average of 10%, 2) The character of discipline has increased by an average of 9% and 3) The character of honesty increased by an average of 7%. Meanwhile, students who developed according to expectations (BSH) and developed very well (BSB) from the three variables increased by an average of 86%,

Based on the results of research at the 1st, 2nd and 3rd meetings according to the diagram in Figure 5 as follows:

Figure 5: Diagram of Character Formation Achievements

From the picture. 5 above, it can be concluded that the development stage of student character formation has increased in research I, II and III. This is proven by the changes that have occurred in students' understanding, where students have become accustomed to a disciplined attitude, an honest attitude, and an attitude of caring about the environment. Overall, the researchers can explain, among other things:

- a) The honesty character of the first research meeting increased to an average of 20% in the second research and increased by 23% in the third research, so the average increase was 32%.
- b) The disciplinary character of the 1st research meeting increased to an average of 24% in the 2nd research and increased 30% in the 3rd research, so the average increase was 40%.
- c) The environmentally caring character from the first research meeting increased to an average of 20% in the second research and increased to 33% in the third research, so the average increase was 35%.

Overall the average score for the character of honesty is 8.0, the character for discipline is an average of 7.7 and the character for caring for the environment is an average of 8.1. Researchers can conclude that there are still some students who need to be made aware that character education is very important in everyday life, in the world of education, in society and in the world of work.

3.2 Discussion

In this research, the data collected is adjusted to the needs of analysis, namely environmental analysis of character education. Below we will present the results of research on the influence of the environment on character education in fourth semester class A students of the Tourism Department, Bali State Polytechnic Hospitality Study Program.

Environmental Influence on Character Education.

Table 2: Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	pre_test	6.470	30	.3958	.0723
	post_test	7.463	30	.2385	.0435

- The average pretest score is 6.470
- The average posttest score is 7.463

Table 3: Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	pre_test & post_test	30	.068	.720

Table 4: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 pre_test - post_test	-.9933	.4479	.0818	-1.1606	-.8261	-12.146	29	.000

T test paired test

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$ or the average pretest and posttest scores are the same

$H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$ or the average pretest and posttest scores are different

With the paired t test, the degrees of freedom used are $df=29$ as in the output and the t table value = 2.363846073. Because it uses a 2-way test, H_0 is rejected when the calculated t value is < -2.363 or $t \text{ calculated} > 2.363$, t count = -12.146 according to the SPSS output, so the conclusions obtained by Reject H_0 or the average pretest and posttest scores are different.

Based on the t test, the results show that there is an environmental influence on character education.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the campus environment has proven to influence the formation of student character. This is proven from the results of learning and observations made by observers where at meetings I, II and III it was seen that:

- a) The honesty character of the research meeting I increased to an average of 20% in research II and increased 23% in research III, so the average increase is 32%.
- b) The disciplinary character of the 1st research meeting increased to an average of 24% in the 2nd research and increased 30% in the 3rd research, so the average increase was 40%.
- c) The environmentally caring character from the first research meeting increased to an average of 20% in the second research and increased to 33% in the third research, so the average increase was 35%. Overall, the average score for the character of honesty is 8.0, the character for discipline is an average of 7.7 and the character for caring for the environment is an average of 8.1.

With the t paired test, the value t table = 2.363846073 and tcount = -12.146, so that the conclusion obtained is reject H_0 or the average pretest and post test scores are different. Based on the t test, the results show that there is an environmental influence on character education.

Thus, the campus environment has an important influence on the formation of student character. Meanwhile, based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with teaching lecturers, they received positive responses, where these responses showed that character building had been carried out in the campus environment by lecturers by providing good role models for students.

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